

LEGAL ANALYSIS OF THE CONCEPT AND TYPES OF IMPLIABILITY IN CRIMES

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Abstract. The article provides a legal definition of the concept of involvement in a crime and persons involved in a crime. It is studied to what extent the involvement in a crime affects responsibility. The issue of concealment of the committed crime, non-reporting of preparing and committed crimes is also considered.

Key words: crime, rule of law, touching the crime, criminal liability, suspect person, court.

Аннотация. Мақолада жиноятга дахлдорлик ва жиноятга дахлдор шахслар тушунчаларига ҳуқуқий таъриф берилган. Жиноятга дахлдорликнинг жавобгарликка таъсир этиш даражаси ўрганилган. Шунингдек, содир этилган жиноятни яширганлик, тайёргарлик кўрилатган ва содир этилган жиноятлар ҳақида хабар бермаслик масаласи кўриб чиқилган.

Калит сўзлар: жиноят, қонун устуворлиги, жиноятга дахлдорлик, жиноий жавобгарлик, гумонланувчи шахс, суд.

Аннотация. В статье дается правовое определение понятий причастности к преступлению и лиц, причастных к преступлению. Изучено, в какой степени влияет на ответственность причастность к преступлению. Также рассмотрен вопрос о сокрытии совершенного преступления, несообщении о готовящихся и совершаемых преступлениях.

Ключевые слова: преступление, верховенство закона, прикосновенность к преступлению, уголовная ответственность, подозреваемый, суд.

As is known, in order to determine the possibilities of effective application of the institution of involvement in a crime, its concept is important in criminal law. However, in the legal literature there are opinions that “the institution of involvement in a crime does not really exist.” In particular, A. V. Naumov states that “there is no clarity in the concept of involvement in a crime.” In his opinion, there is no need to define the concept of complicity in a crime in criminal law, since crimes with independent content are considered forms of complicity¹.

However, if you look into the problem from this point of view, you cannot agree with the opinion of the

authors who argue that “the institution of involvement in a crime does not really exist.” Because the actions associated with the crime are real and cannot be refuted. From this point of view, most legal scholars now recognize complicity in a crime as an independent institution of criminal law.

Therefore, we can agree with the opinion of M. Usmonaliev that “involvement in a crime is not an element of the institution of complicity, but a separate institution of criminal law”².

In our opinion, the effectiveness of the fight against crimes related to crime can only be realized by defining its legal features in the law.

¹ See: Наумов А.В. Уголовное право. Общая часть. – М., 1996. – С. 56.

² See: Усмоналиев М. Жиноят ҳуқуқи: Умумий қисм. Олий ўқув юртлари учун дарслик. – Т.: “Янги аср авлоди”, 2005. – 296-б.

Therefore, it is advisable to develop a concept that reveals the legal features of the institution of complicity in a crime and fix it in the criminal law through a separate norm.

Some authors do not give a clear definition of who the persons involved in the crime mean. When M. Usmonaliev defined he meant that involvement in a crime, the suspect did not take part in a crime committed or committed by in other persons, but he clearly knew that they were preparing for a crime, to commit a crime, without giving a promise in advance, without informing the authorities, as well as the criminal, a tool crime, emphasizes that it should be understood to conceal the traces of a crime or things obtained by criminal means without a prior promise. However, in our opinion, this definition does not cover all forms of participation in a crime. That is, this definition does not focus on the commission of a crime³.

Article 31 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation provides for two types of participation in a crime: 1) failure to report a crime without a prior promise; 2) concealment of a criminal, weapons and means of crime, traces of a crime or things obtained by criminal means, without a prior promise.

If we turn to the opinion of scientists on this matter, the person concerned committed a crime or did not participate in a crime committed by other persons, but clearly realizing that he is preparing for a crime, he commits a crime without notifying the authorities without making an advance promise, as well as a criminal one, the crime consists in concealing weapons, traces of a crime or things obtained by criminal means, without a prior promise.

According to M.Kh. Rustamboev, “participation in a crime is a form of criminal participation, causally not connected with the act of the guilty, expressed in failure to report a crime without a preliminary promise, concealment of a criminal without a preliminary promise, admission of a crime without a preliminary promise,” an advance promise.

Persons who did not participate in the commission of a crime, but who are related to it, are involved in the crime⁴.

According to A. S. Yakubov, “involvement in a crime is understood as involvement in a crime com-

mitted by other persons without participation in them”⁵.

The group of authors interprets “involvement in a crime as a deliberate act related to a crime, committed by a person without a prior promise, but did not contribute to its commission.” Others interpret involvement in a crime as a socially dangerous activity of a person. However, in our opinion, involvement in a crime cannot be considered as an activity, since its forms are failure to report a crime, and the commission of a crime is committed in an act of inaction. At the same time, it is wrong to evaluate actions performed in inaction as activity. Therefore, involvement in a crime should be assessed as an act.

There are two types of criminal activity. In particular, not inform the authorities about the preparation of a crime, the commission of a crime, or the commission of a crime without a prior promise.

The Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides for two types of participation: failure to report a crime to the relevant authorities without a prior promise and concealment of a crime without a prior promise. Some authors single out the commission of a crime as a separate type of complicity.

However, the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan does not provide for the commission of a crime as a separate type of participation. In our opinion, it is right that such a situation is not provided for by law as a type of involvement. Because of non-admission, if it is the responsibility of the one, who allowed it, can be held accountable for a cold attitude towards one's duty.

Every citizen is obliged to prevent crimes, if this is not part of his duties. If a citizen does not fulfill the obligation imposed on him and the committed act is a grave or especially grave crime, the citizen is liable only in cases provided for by Articles 1551 and 241 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation.

Concealment without prior promise of a criminal, weapons and means of crime, traces of a crime or things obtained by criminal means is the basis of liability.

Close relatives of the suspect, accused or defendant are not liable for failure to report a crime or concealment of a crime without a prior promise.

³ Ibid.

⁴ See: Рустамбоев М.Х. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Жиноят кодексига шарҳлар. Махсус қисм. – Т.: “Илм зиё”, 2006. – 415-б.

⁵ See: Якубов А.С. Учение о преступлении по законодательству Республики Узбекистан. –Т.: Академия МВД. 1995. – С. 45.

It should be noted that in both cases, active measures are taken to cover up the underlying crime. However, the presence or absence of a causal link between the activities of the person who covered up the crime and the concealed crime is of decisive importance here. Some jurists (in particular, A.S. Yakubov) single out the commission of a crime as a separate type of participation, thereby emphasizing the existence of three types of this institution. Some authors (A.D. Makarov), based on their point of view on the types of involvement, include the acquisition or transfer of property knowingly obtained by criminal means, without a preliminary promise, as well as money or property obtained by criminal means, to types of concealment. means disclosure (legalization). This provision is also reflected in some textbooks and commentaries on criminal law. For example, the Criminal Code provides for another form of participation in a crime - the possession or transfer of property knowingly obtained by criminal means.

This is a special form compared to concealing a crime.” In another interpretation, the types of concealment of a crime include the storage or transfer of these items and material values. A. E. Milin similarly notes: “By its legal nature, the possession or transfer of property knowingly obtained by criminal means has all the signs of involvement in a crime, and is considered a separate form, different from its other forms”⁶. At the same time, the LC proposed the following definition of the concept of involvement in a crime: “Involvement in a crime refers to crimes provided for by criminal law, guiltily committed, preparing, being committed or completed, but not contributing to its preparation and commission, therefore, criminal of socially dangerous acts, not connected by a causal relationship neither with the result, nor with the criminal act or inaction itself.

However, Article 31 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan does not include such forms as the commission of a crime and the legalization of property obtained by criminal means, as a form of participation in a crime. In this regard, M. Usmonaliev notes that the positive point is that this situation is not provided for by law as a type of complicity, since if obstruction is within the scope of a person’s official

duties, he can be held accountable by accusing him with a cold look at his duties⁷.

From this it is clear that if the inaction belongs to the sphere of official duties of a person, it will be assessed and qualified as a case of a separate corpus delicti, and not as involvement in a crime. For example, looting, damage or destruction of property as a result of a person’s dishonest performance of duties related to the protection of property (Article 172 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation) and so on is considered an unfair attitude towards the protection of property. If prevention is not the responsibility of a person, it should be noted that every citizen is obliged to prevent crimes.

In addition, part 1 of article 40 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides for the legal procedure for the appeal of public associations and communities, their governing bodies and representatives to the investigative body, investigator, prosecutor or court with information about the crime committed or getting ready. It is known that a public association is a voluntary structure created as a result of the free will of the united citizens for the joint exercise of their rights, freedoms, as well as legitimate interests in politics, economics, social development, science, culture, ecology and other areas of life. Communities, on the other hand, are literally groups of citizens who have a mutual interest in uniting. It can be seen that the WPC, as members of public associations and communities, are directly responsible for informing citizens about crime. In addition, according to Article 48 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the constitutional duty of citizens is to comply with the Constitution and laws, respect for the rights, freedoms, honor and dignity of others. Also, in many legal books it is stated that “non-reporting is an act contrary to morality, since it is the duty of every citizen to report a crime.” Therefore, the obligation of citizens to report crimes to law enforcement agencies should be considered not only as a case of humanity, in a general sense, as a civil duty, but also as a case that has appropriate legal grounds from the point of view of criminal law. For this reason, if a citizen does not fulfill the duty assigned to him and the committed act is a grave or especially grave crime, the person

⁶ See: Милин А.Е. Уголовная ответственность за приобретение или сбыт имущества, заведомо добытого преступным путем: Дис. канд. юрид. наук. – М., 2004. – С. 74.

⁷ See: Усмоналиев М. Жиноят ҳуқуқи: Умумий қисм. Олий ўқув юртлари учун дарслик. – Т.: “Янги аср авлоди”, 2005. - 296-б.

will be found guilty of failure to report a crime under Article 241 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Belarus. Uzbekistan and will be prosecuted. For this reason, avoidance should not be considered as a separate kind of engagement. It can also be noted that in many foreign countries, in particular in the Russian Federation, the attraction institution of involvement in a crime is traditionally divided into two types.

In turn, it should be noted that the excessive expansion of the institution of involvement in a crime and the type of concealment of a crime creates difficulties in qualifying the actions of perpetrators. In addition, possession or transfer of property knowingly obtained by criminal means and disclosure (legalization) of money and property obtained by criminal means are independent elements of a crime.

A clear understanding of the concept and types of involvement in a crime makes it possible to distinguish the events covered by its content, both from participation in a crime and from actions that do not entail criminal liability. Like any scientific abstraction, the concept of involvement in a crime is a necessary step in the process of knowing its specific forms, serves as

a theoretical basis for determining their nature and the correct application of the criminal law in practice.

If you express your opinion more clearly, then on the system of complicity in a crime (Article 31 of the Criminal Code), despite the fact that it is placed in Chapter VI of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, i.e. "Participation in a crime" is not an element of the institution of complicity, but is considered a separate criminal law institution. In this regard, according to Professor M. Kh. Rustamboev, "involvement differs from participation in that the persons involved in the crime, although are in a certain relation to the committed crime, but are not causally connected with it, do not contribute to the emergence of a criminal result"⁸.

Therefore, it is understood as taking into account the foregoing, the concept of complicity in a crime can be defined as follows: without a prior promise or concealment of the person who committed it.

If this concept of involvement in a crime is not defined well and developed in the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it may cause the violation of human rights of a suspect, criminal or defendant.

⁸ See: Рустамбоев М.Х. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Жиноят кодексига шарҳлар. Махсус қисм. – Т.: "Илм зиё", 2006. – 415-б.